

TITLE: Time-Varying Associations between Lead and Risk of Alzheimer’s Disease Mortality in Massachusetts: An Ecological Study at the Municipality Level

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Abstract

Background: The role of lead (Pb) exposure in the risk of Alzheimer's disease (AD) is unclear. While excessive lead exposure has been suggested as a potential risk factor, it is also conceivable that lead may competitively inhibit the uptake of other toxic metals, thereby reducing the risk of AD.

Methods: We conducted an ecological study in Massachusetts examining the association between municipality-level AD mortality among seniors aged ≥ 75 years (2015-2019) and elevated blood lead levels (EBLL) among seniors annually (2002-2014). We used EBLL of children aged < 6 years as a proxy. We controlled for haloacetic acid-five (HAA5) exposure which provided a measure of chlorinated water treatment. Other time-invariant control variables included overall mortality, number of assisted living and nursing home beds per elderly population, percentage of Black residents, population density, income. Least squares linear regression was used to examine the association between EBLL, HAA5, their interaction, and AD mortality for each year from 2002-2014.

Results: Annual mean EBLL among eligible municipalities decreased from 15.21% (SD: 6.95%, $n = 200$) in 2002 to 2.03% (SD: 2.07%, $n = 150$) in 2014. EBLL demonstrated an inverse association with AD mortality for each year, with the strength of this association, based on parameter estimates, increasing annually from 2002 to 2014 ($R^2 = 0.62$, P-trend: < 0.01). HAA5 was also negatively associated with AD mortality. A significant EBLL-HAA5 interaction was observed, which in contrast, was positively associated with AD mortality, and became more pronounced in later years.

Conclusions: For the first time, lead, as well as HAA5, were shown to be inversely associated with AD mortality. These findings may imply that EBLL or the presence of HAA5 may limit individual level exposure to other metals, however, as an ecological study, individual-level inferences are limited due to potential confounding.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease (AD); lead (Pb); haloacetic acids-five (HAA5), metals

Key Messages

What is already known on this topic:

- Studies investigating the association of blood lead levels and Alzheimer's disease are scarce.
- A previous NHANES study reported an increased risk of Alzheimer's disease mortality associated with lead exposure, however, although the results were not statistically significant.
- A cross-sectional study from Iran found increased blood lead among those with Alzheimer's disease, but this study was confounded by substance abuse among participants.

What this study adds:

- Contrary to existing literature, the findings from this study suggest that lead exposure is associated with a reduced risk of Alzheimer's disease mortality.
- Haloacetic acids-five, a byproduct of water chlorination, were associated with decreased risk of Alzheimer's disease mortality.

How this study might affect research, practice or policy:

- Prospective studies should investigate the impact of reduced overall essential metal uptake on the risk of Alzheimer's disease development and progression.

1. Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by progressive and severe dementia [1]. Though many risk factors for AD have been found, the ultimate cause(s) of AD pathogenesis remains elusive [2–4]. There are strong genetic risk factors, such as apolipoprotein $\epsilon 4$ (apo $\epsilon 4$), but it is likely that this gene interacts with other environmental risk factors [5].

Metals have been found in altered concentrations within brain tissue, cerebrospinal fluid, blood serum, and urine of subjects with AD [2,3,6–8]. Though the association between dysregulation of metal homeostasis or environmental metal exposure and AD has been exhaustively studied, no systematic deviation has been recognized and a mechanism of pathogenesis has not been established [4]. Such is the state of research that it is not yet known if these metal abnormalities are causal to or resultant of pathologic processes of AD.

If we view metals as central to the pathoetiology of the disease, then it is possible that exposure to a certain metal, more prevalent in developing than developed countries, may be causal of the discrepancies found in the prevalence of AD among these countries. Leaded gasoline was phased-out in developed countries beginning in the 1970s due to concern over potential damage to children's health [9]. However, many developing countries did not begin to ban leaded gasoline until later [10]. For instance, Nigeria first began its phase-out in 2002 and as late as 2014 leaded gasoline was still present at 0.49-1.90 mg/L [11]. As such, in a study from Nigeria in 2005, mean blood lead level (BLL) in non-occupationally exposed adults was 33 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ [12]. A meta-analysis of studies from 2010-2018 in India, where leaded gasoline was phased out in 2000, found a mean BLL among non-occupationally exposed adults of 7.52 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ [13]. In comparison, geometric mean BLL in US adults decreased from 1.68 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ (95% CI=1.63, 1.74) to 0.82 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ (95% CI=0.77, 0.87) from 1999-2016 [14]. In accordance with the hypothesis, a 1992 study from Ibadan,

Nigeria found an AD prevalence of 1.41% among those aged ≥ 65 years, but a significantly higher rate of 6.24% was found among Blacks in Indianapolis, Indiana in a corresponding study [15]. Similarly, a study in northern India from 1998 found an AD incidence of 4.7 per 1000 person-years versus a rate of 17.5 per 1000 person-years in Pennsylvania [16].

This reduction in lead may not only be the cause of the discrepancy in prevalence between developed and developing countries, but also the main factor for the global rise in prevalence of AD in recent decades. It is common to think of AD as increasing in prevalence due to increasing lifespan. However, even age-adjusted prevalence of AD has increased greatly over just a short time. In the US, age-standardized rates of AD increased among Medicare beneficiaries between the years 1984-1990 and 1991-2000 by 73% [17].

The protection that lead putatively offers an individual may be mediated by its reduction to exposure of AD-causing metals by competitive transportation through transporters, such as the divalent metal transporter-1 (DMT-1). This transporter can be found within the gut where it can effect systemic levels of particular metals, but is also found at the subcellular level within organelles, such as the mitochondria [18,19].

Accordingly, in the present study, we observed if the presence of lead offers any protective capacity against risk of AD. We also assessed whether other processes which have the effect of reducing overall exposure to metals can similarly affect the risk of AD.

2. Methods

We conducted an ecological study within the US state of Massachusetts to investigate the relationship of lead exposure and risk of AD death. Massachusetts is situated in New England with

a population of around 7 million who mainly reside within the eastern portion of the state. The state was chosen due to its large number of municipalities, enabling a robust analysis.

2.1. AD Mortality

The annual number of persons aged ≥ 75 years living in each municipality was derived by multiplying the total annual population estimates by the percentage of persons aged ≥ 75 years for the year 2015, each of which was sourced from the University of Massachusetts Donahue Institute [20]. Only municipalities with ≥ 600 persons aged ≥ 75 years were selected.

Municipality-level cause of death among Massachusetts residents aged ≥ 75 years for the years 2015-2019 was sourced from the Population Health Information Tool dataset of the Massachusetts Department of Public Health, Registry of Vital Records and Statistics [21]. Data were collected from individual death certificates of Massachusetts residents, including residents who died in other US states. Cause of death information was based on the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10) mortality data codes. Though data for the years 2020-2021 were available, they were excluded due to the COVID-19 epidemic which would likely have greatly distorted the investigation due to excess deaths within these years.

We derived the overall percentage of persons with AD mortality across the full 5-year period (i.e., 2015-2019) by dividing the number of AD deaths by the total number of deaths among persons aged ≥ 75 years. We used this 5-year period rather than any single year as AD mortality may be complicated by factors unrelated to the pathogenesis of AD (e.g., annual influenza risk).

2.2. Lead Exposure

Next, a proxy level of lead exposure was ascertained for each municipality as adult lead data was unavailable. The annual incidence of children aged < 6 years with elevated blood lead level (EBLL)

≥ 5 ug/dl in years 2002-2014 at the municipality level was sourced from the Massachusetts Executive Office of Health and Human Services [22]. EBLL was derived on an annual basis only for municipalities which screened ≥ 100 children for that particular year. Instances in which there were only 1-6 children with an EBLL between 5-10 ug/dl were censored. There were an increased number of municipalities with censored values as time progressed due to fewer children having an EBLL of 5 ug/dl or greater. The following algorithm was used to derive the EBLL for each municipality: (i) the combined (i.e., confirmed and unconfirmed) 5-10 ug/dl EBLL rates for all children (male and female) was extracted; (ii) if the combined rates were censored, just the unconfirmed rates or confirmed rates (in that order) for all children were then applied; (iii) if all of the above were censored, then female only or male only rates were applied towards the final EBLL rate in the same pattern of availability (i.e., combined rate first, followed by unconfirmed and then confirmed rates); (iv) incidence of children with EBLs >10 ug/dl was determined and added to the 5-10 ug/dl EBLL incidence rate.

2.3. Water Contaminant Exposure

Tap water contains dozens of trace elements and organic compounds which come from surface runoff, passage through rocks and sediment, water treatment, and piping. This can be a major source of various metal exposures that have the potential to modify risk of AD. Total concentration of haloacetic acids-five (HAA5), being a byproduct of disinfection, may give an indication of the level of chlorination and removal of metals such as Mn and Fe [23]. Therefore, finished (i.e., treated) drinking water levels of total HAA5 were extracted for the years 2000-2019; the number of water samples above various thresholds of concentration was examined for the entire period of extraction. As the municipalities of Abington and Rockland share a water supply, the extracted results from Rockland were also applied to Abington.

2.4. Confounders

As some seniors may have switched official residence after moving into nursing homes or assisted living facilities, with municipalities with more beds taking on a larger burden of patients with AD, the model was also adjusted by the number of total beds within each municipality. The number of beds within each municipality was ascertained using the facility search function of the Massachusetts Senior Care Association web portal [24]. This was then divided by the average number of persons aged ≥ 75 years for the years 2015-2019 to derive a rate of persons per available bed.

Population density was used a proxy of vehicle pollution exposure and was derived from US Census data for 2010 [25]. The percentage of Black population within each municipality was derived from US Census data for 2020 [26]. Gross domestic product per capita was used to measure socioeconomic status and was sourced from the 2017-2021 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates [27]. Overall percentage of population who died from 2015-2019 from any cause was derived.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

2.5.1 Spatial Analysis

To evaluate the existence of geographical patterns in AD mortality, EBLL, and HAA5 levels across municipalities, global and local spatial autocorrelation analyses were performed. Global Moran's I statistic measures the overall degree of spatial clustering present. The Anselin local Moran's I identifies specific locations of hot spots (high-high), cold spots (low-low), and spatial outliers (high-low or low-high). These statistics were calculated in ArcGIS Pro. To conduct these analyses

we selected the year 2008, selecting all municipalities with ≥ 600 persons aged ≥ 75 in which ≥ 100 children were screened for blood lead.

2.5.2 Regression Analysis

Univariate models were fitted using least squares regression with the time-invariant mean AD mortality rate from 2015-2019 as the dependent variable and time-varying annual EBLI incidence applied as independent variables for each year from 2002-2014. Next, models were adjusted for several potential confounders, including persons per available bed, population density, race, income, mean overall death from 2015-2019, and HAA5. Finally, adjusted models were fitted with an additional interaction term between HAA5 and EBLI.

All regressions analyses were ordinary least squares and were performed with SAS[®] OnDemand for Academics. The results of regression analysis were represented by β regression coefficients, standard error, and *P*-value. Significance was set at $P < 0.05$. As this was a population-level study, no ethics approval was necessary.

Patient and public involvement

No participants were involved in setting the research questions or outcome measures, or in the design and implementation of the study. No plans exist to involve patients in dissemination.

3. Results

Of 351 municipalities in Massachusetts, 303 municipalities had a population of ≥ 600 persons aged ≥ 75 years from 2015-2019, and 218 of these had ≥ 10 samples of the disinfection byproduct HAA5.

The number of municipalities with available BLL data ranged from 143-205 each year from 2002-2014, based on an annual screening population of ≥ 100 children (Table 1). The mean annual percentage of EBLL declined from 15.21% ($\pm 6.95\%$) in 2002 to 2.03% ($\pm 2.07\%$) in 2014. Figure 1 maps the distribution AD mortality, EBLL, and HAA5 levels across municipalities.

3.1 Spatial Analyses

Global spatial autocorrelation analysis found significant clustering of AD mortality rates, EBLL (in 2008), and HAA5 levels (Moran's I, $P < 0.0001$ for each). However, local cluster analyses indicated high-high and low-low clusters did not correspond well across these variables (Figure 2). For example, high AD mortality clusters were seen in central/southeastern regions, while high EBLL clusters occurred in some peripheral areas, and elevated HAA5 clusters in northeastern/southeastern parts of the state.

3.2 Regression Analyses

Separate multivariate linear regressions were fitted for the years 2002-2014, with EBLL as the primary predictor variable and AD mortality as the outcome. Without EBLL-HAA5 interaction, higher EBLL was associated with lower AD mortality, peaking in 2008 ($\beta = -0.0699$, se: 0.03, $P < 0.05$) six years before AD mortality assessment began. This inverse association strengthened from 2002 through 2008 ($R^2 = 0.78$ for estimates, 0.68 for t-values, Figure 3a) but then decreased in magnitude but with greater fluctuation ($R^2 = 0.53$ for estimates, 0.53 for t-values, Figure 3b). The time-invariant covariate HAA5 was also inversely associated with AD mortality across all years.

When including the EBLL-HAA5 interaction term, there was a positive association with AD mortality, and the interaction coefficient (β interaction) increased in magnitude from 2002 to 2014

as AD assessment years approached (2014 β interaction = 0.8648, $p < 0.001$). Figures 4a-b show 2002-2014 plots for estimate and t-value, including trends.

4. Discussion

In this ecological time-series study of Massachusetts municipalities from 2002 through 2014, we investigated the potential roles of lead exposure and water chlorination in mitigating the risk of AD mortality. The study was motivated by the hypothesis that exposure to certain metals may contribute to the development of AD, and reducing exposure to these metals could potentially lower the risk. We proposed that lead exposure and the chlorination of drinking water, which generates haloacetic acids (HAA5) as a byproduct, may be two key factors that reduce exposure to other toxic metals implicated in AD pathogenesis. We found that proxy estimates of elevated blood lead levels (EBLL) were inversely associated with risk of AD mortality, suggesting a protective effect of lead exposure. Notably, the presence of HAA5 in drinking water was also associated with a reduced risk of AD-related deaths. Furthermore, an interaction between HAA5 and EBLL was evident, suggesting a potential modifying effect.

4.1 Temporal dynamics of AD risk factors

The observed trends in the coefficients (parameter estimates) and t-values of EBLL provide valuable insights into the temporal dynamics of risk factors. The upward trend from 2002 to 2008, followed by a downward trend from 2008 to 2014, suggests a critical period when several factors were balanced. Firstly, due to the extended time frame in which AD develops, blood lead exposure proximal to mortality assessment may not accurately reflect the degree of lead exposure contributing to disease initiation and progression. Secondly, as EBLL levels decreased over time, individuals may have become more susceptible to the influence of other risk factors; this is

supported by the strengthening EBLL-HAA5 interaction, suggesting a potential modifying effect at lower BLL. With this interaction term, EBLL alone became significantly inversely associated with AD-related deaths from 2008-2014, except for 2012. Thirdly, as the time series approached the period of AD mortality assessment, the EBLL data became increasingly relevant and potentially more predictive of AD risk. These findings highlight the importance of considering temporal dynamics of risk factors and potential interactions in risk factors in chronic diseases like AD. It should be noted that a possible explanation for the increased variability in estimates and t-values in the latter years of the study may be due to the limitations of the study methodology. It's important to recognize that our EBLL estimates are proxies based on children's data. As BLL declined precipitously over the study period, actual lead levels in seniors may have drifted from proxy levels due to the emergence of point sources of lead exposure becoming ever more significant.

4.2 Lead and metal absorption

While we should exercise caution in directly inferring individual-level effects from population-level indicators due to potential confounding factors, the collective evidence strongly suggests that decreased bioavailability of certain metals, has an inhibitory effect on the risk of AD development and mortality. Evidence of lead's reduction of metals is somewhat limited. Although iron deficiency increases the risk of lead poisoning, lead poisoning is also associated with anemia [28–30]. Thus, the causality is questionable. However, a study from India revealed that lead might also decrease the absorption of other essential metals, with children having a BLL of ≥ 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ more likely to have anemia and substantially lower calcium and zinc than those with a BLL < 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ [31]. This suggests that lead exposure may disrupt the absorption of multiple essential metals,

contributing to the observed association between reduced lead exposure and decreased AD mortality risk.

4.3 HAA5 and water treatment

Although HAA5 can be ingested through drinking water, its role in the diminishment of metal exposure is likely indirect, owing to its formation as a byproduct of chlorinated water treatment processes. Chlorination products oxidize soluble iron (II) and manganese (II), forming insoluble iron hydroxide and manganese oxide precipitates, which are typically removed by filtration. During this process, HAA5 can form from the dissolved organic carbon present in the water [32,33]. In the current study, the interaction between HAA5 and EBL—which, in contrast to each variable alone, is positively associated with AD mortality—suggests that the water treatment process also facilitates the removal of lead.

4.4 Previous literature

Only two studies in the literature have attempted to study the effects of BLL on risk of AD or AD mortality. The first, a study from Iran, tested BLL found mean BLL to be higher in those with AD compared to controls (AD: 22.22 ug/dL vs. control: 7.88 ug/dL)[34]. However, this study had a significant confounder in that a large portion of each group was abusing opium which is particularly high in lead content. BLL in abusers was greater among those with AD (54.5 ug/dl [41.9-78.5] than other study participants (7.15 ug/dl [5.20-13.30]). The second study, a longitudinal National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) investigation by Horton et al., found BLL to be increased in those who eventually died from AD, though this was not statistically significant [35]. Study participants were accrued from 1999-2008. Importantly, as BLL has been gradually decreasing over the last several decades, the study may have been confounded by giving unequal follow-up time to participants with different levels of lead exposure.

Nevertheless, some investigations have showed an association between excess lead exposure and cognitive impairment and neuropsychiatric symptoms [36,37]. These studies were typically located within occupational settings where levels of lead were unusually high. For instance, Fenga et al. found a mean BLL of 56.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ in lead exposed workers compared to 15.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ in matched adults [36]. Most studies investigating BLL among the general population have not found associations between BLL and cognitive decline; however, some studies have found a relationship between bone lead and cognitive impairment [38–40]. Thus, it may be possible that exceedingly high levels of lead contribute to a form of cognitive impairment that is entirely different from AD. Studies linking drinking water levels of specific metals to risk of AD feature prominently in the literature. For over two decades associations between aluminum and AD have been investigated [41,42]. More recently, copper and zinc have entered contention as possible contributors to AD pathogenesis; accordingly, these metals have been studied in both humans and mouse models involving drinking water [43,44]. Interestingly, silicon was found to be associated with decreased risk of AD when individuals were also exposed to aluminum, possibly by reducing bioavailability of the latter [45].

4.5 Challenges in metal investigations

Metal investigations are complex, not least of which is due to concentrations varying with the presence of other metals, often due to competitive cellular transportation [46]. Making metal investigations even more difficult is the differing blood serum half-lives of metals. For instance, while lead has a long half-life of 35 days, that of manganese is less than two hours [47]. Moreover, previously absorbed metals can leach from bone into blood after periods of remodeling [48]. Due to these methodological limitations, studies have failed to consistently describe the role of essential metals in AD [4]. Though excess essential metal exposure is a likely risk factor for AD, there are

some unresolved questions such as why these metals are often found to be decreased in blood serum but increased in senile plaques [49,50].

4.6 Limitations

There are several limitations to this study, but these are also well-weighted against its strengths. As an ecological study, the design has its own set of usual limitations. Individual patient data was not directly explored, and risk of ecological fallacy is always present. Therefore, results must be interpreted with caution. However, potential bias was limited by the incorporation of economic and race indicators as well as the addition of other potential confounders to the models, such as the number of nursing home and assisted living beds and overall death. It is known that AD develops over the course of years, and patients will often live with the condition for several years after diagnosis. Due to data constraints, we were limited to using risk of AD death instead of the more reliable AD incidence rate. Thus, it is impossible to state definitively whether lead slowed the progression of AD or merely limited the onset of the disease. Additionally, proxy levels of EBLL were derived for each municipality, and do not reflect actual EBLL incidence in seniors. Finally, HAA5 is also only acting as a proxy for chlorinated water and indirectly represents the elimination of metal contaminants. Thus, we cannot know with precision which metals were reduced.

Conclusion

Using an ecological design, we assessed the association of elevated blood lead and exposure to drinking water contaminants with AD-related mortality in Massachusetts municipalities. The observed inverse association between EBLL and AD mortality, coupled with the protective effect of HAA5, underscores the potential for reducing exposure to certain metals and chemical contaminants as a means of lowering the risk of AD-related mortality. This is the first study to

reveal such associations with AD. However, the ecological design of this study requires us to interpret the results with caution. As such, the findings have great potential ramifications for public health, but individual- or multi-level studies are necessary to make inferences regarding causality. Indeed, as lead exposure around the world is decreasing rapidly the window of opportunity for studying lead exposure in seniors at higher levels is closing. As the number of individuals with AD is expected to climb with our aging population, and as lead continues to decrease, it may severely strain the capacity of healthcare systems.

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Data sharing statement: Data have been shared in Supplementary file.

Figure 1. Spatial patterns of Alzheimer's disease mortality, elevated blood lead levels, and drinking water contaminants in selected Massachusetts municipalities.

A. Mean Alzheimer's disease mortality rate from 2015-2019.

B. Prevalence of elevated blood lead levels (EBLL ≥ 5 $\mu\text{g/dL}$) among children aged <6 years screened in 2008.

C. Percentage of drinking water samples with total haloacetic acids (HAA5) concentration ≥ 1 $\mu\text{g/L}$, from 2000-2019.

Municipalities included met the following criteria: population ≥ 600 persons aged ≥ 75 years, at least 10 water samples with measured HAA5 levels, and ≥ 100 children aged <6 years screened for blood lead levels in 2008.

Figure 2. Spatial clustering patterns of Alzheimer's disease mortality, elevated blood lead levels, and drinking water contaminants as assessed by Anselin Local Moran's I analysis.

A. Clustering of mean Alzheimer's disease mortality from 2015-2019 (n = 253 municipalities).

B. Clustering of the prevalence of elevated blood lead levels (EBLL ≥ 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$) among children aged <6 years screened in 2008 (n = 253 municipalities).

C. Clustering of the rate of drinking water samples with total haloacetic acids (HAA5) concentration ≥ 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$, from 2000-2019 (n = 200 municipalities).

Figure 3. Temporal trends in the association between elevated blood lead levels and Alzheimer's disease mortality from multivariable regression models.

A. Parameter estimates (with standard errors) for the association between elevated blood lead levels (EBLL) and the square root of mean Alzheimer's disease mortality rate from 2015-2019, by year.

B. T-values for the EBLL parameter estimates, by year.

The multivariable linear regression models were adjusted for the following covariates: rate of drinking water samples with total haloacetic acids (HAA5) concentration $\geq 1 \mu\text{g/L}$, nursing home and assisted living bed rate, natural logarithm of population density, percentage of Black population, per capita gross domestic product (GDP), and percentage of population dying from other causes from 2015-2019.

Trend analyses of EBLL parameter estimates and associated t-values are provided for the periods 2002-2008 and 2008-2014. The panel also displays the prevalence of EBLL at the municipality level for each year.

Figure 4. Temporal trends in the association between elevated blood lead levels and Alzheimer's disease mortality from multivariable regression models with EBLL-HAA5 interaction term.

A. Parameter estimates (with standard errors) for the EBLL-HAA5 interaction term and the square root of mean Alzheimer's disease mortality rate from 2015-2019, by year.

B. T-values for the EBLL-HAA5 interaction term parameter estimates, by year.

The multivariable linear regression models were adjusted for the following covariates: rate of drinking water samples with total haloacetic acids (HAA5) concentration $\geq 1 \mu\text{g/L}$, nursing home and assisted living bed rate, natural logarithm of population density, percentage of Black population, per capita gross domestic product (GDP), and percentage of population dying from other causes from 2015-2019.

Trend analyses of EBLL parameter estimates and associated t-values are provided for full period from 2002-2014. The panel also displays the prevalence of EBLL at the municipality level for each year.

Table 1. Mean elevated blood lead in children <6 years, by year

Year	n	Mean	Std
2002	200	15.21%	6.95%
2003	205	12.49%	5.59%
2004	203	12.63%	6.85%
2005	203	10.45%	6.03%
2006	201	9.47%	5.91%
2007	201	7.62%	4.83%
2008	200	5.32%	3.57%
2009	194	4.86%	3.51%
2010	178	4.10%	2.69%
2011	164	3.30%	2.42%
2012	161	3.12%	2.17%
2013	143	2.25%	2.01%
2014	150	2.03%	2.07%

Municipalities selected had at least 600 adults aged 75 years or greater, at least 10 samples of haloacetic acids-5 (HAA5), and at least 100 children screened for blood lead level within given year.

Table 2. Results of multivariable linear regression models of square root-transformed mean Alzheimer's disease mortality (2015-2019)

Year of BLL measurement	Variable	Univariate analysis			Multivariate analysis			Multivariate analysis + interaction term		
		Parameter estimate	Standard error	P-value	Parameter estimate	Standard error	P-value	Parameter estimate	Standard error	P-value
2002 (n = 200)	EBLL	-0.01165	0.01359	0.3927	0.0003	0.01575	0.9825	-0.10436	0.04899	0.0344
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0102	0.00327	0.002	-0.02726	0.00822	0.0011
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.1242	0.0551	0.0253
2003 (n = 205)	EBLL	-0.00791	0.01682	0.6389	0.0075	0.01982	0.7053	-0.07186	0.0594	0.2279
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0107	0.00323	0.001	-0.02158	0.0083	0.01
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.09466	0.06681	0.1581
2004 (n = 203)	EBLL	-0.01949	0.01368	0.1557	-0.0240	0.01581	0.1306	-0.07803	0.03889	0.0462
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0097	0.00319	0.0026	-0.01821	0.00642	0.0051
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.06923	0.04555	0.1302
2005 (n = 203)	EBLL	-0.02418	0.01537	0.1174	-0.0278	0.01818	0.1278	-0.09888	0.04674	0.0357
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0091	0.00317	0.0045	-0.01759	0.00603	0.0039
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.08836	0.05358	0.1007
2006 (n = 201)	EBLL	-0.01452	0.01586	0.3609	-0.0130	0.01961	0.5095	-0.17897	0.06346	0.0053
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0096	0.00333	0.0042	-0.0245	0.00632	0.0001
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.18936	0.06896	0.0066
2007 (n = 201)	EBLL	-0.0414	0.01924	0.0326	-0.0480	0.02227	0.0324	-0.14578	0.05748	0.012
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0087	0.00321	0.0075	-0.01697	0.00552	0.0024
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.12356	0.06704	0.0669
2008 (n = 200)	EBLL	-0.06057	0.02618	0.0217	-0.0699	0.03021	0.0218	-0.34105	0.09824	0.0006
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0089	0.00325	0.0068	-0.02296	0.00581	0.0001
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.31443	0.1086	0.0042
2009 (n = 194)	EBLL	-0.03428	0.02716	0.2084	-0.0524	0.03258	0.1093	-0.32247	0.0946	0.0008
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0086	0.00337	0.0116	-0.02253	0.00566	<.0001
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.32931	0.10862	0.0028
2010 (n = 178)	EBLL	0.02401	0.03588	0.5042	0.0257	0.04254	0.5459	-0.3673	0.10346	0.0005
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0088	0.00345	0.0118	-0.02755	0.00561	<.0001
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.49815	0.12058	<.0001
2011 (n = 164)	EBLL	0.00782	0.03916	0.842	0.0555	0.04427	0.2116	-0.31784	0.11032	0.0045
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0107	0.00338	0.0019	-0.02549	0.00519	<.0001
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.46887	0.12778	0.0003
2012 (n = 161)	EBLL	-0.00976	0.04583	0.8317	0.0048	0.05006	0.9235	-0.14189	0.15276	0.3544
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0080	0.00365	0.0293	-0.01311	0.00619	0.0359

	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.1743	0.17147	0.311
2013 (n = 143)	EBLL	-0.0358	0.04833	0.4601	-0.0003	0.0535	0.9955	-0.39359	0.16305	0.0171
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0052	0.00374	0.1696	-0.01367	0.00496	0.0066
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.48512	0.19044	0.012
2014 (n = 150)	EBLL	-0.00562	0.05147	0.9132	0.0595	0.0589	0.3144	-0.71116	0.22188	0.0017
	HAA5	-	-	-	-0.0118	0.00418	0.0054	-0.02245	0.00499	<.0001
	EBLL*HAA5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.86476	0.24075	0.0005

Dependent variable consisted of mean Alzheimer's disease mortality among individuals aged 75 years or greater for the period from 2015-2019. Elevated blood lead level (EBLL) was assessed annually from 2002-2014. Analyses were controlled at the municipality level by time-invariant variables, including percentage of drinking water samples with ≥ 1 ug/L of haloacetic acids-5 (HAA5), nursing home and assisted living bed rate, natural logarithm of population density, percentage Black population, income level in gross domestic product (GDP) per capita, and percentage of population dying from other causes from 2015-2019.